

The organisation of agricultural activity through its registers – Competition aspects of registers and transparency^{*}.

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Abstract

Cette contribution examine les registres fondés sur le droit communautaire et leurs objectifs en ce qui concerne l'octroi d'aides d'État dans le secteur agricole ainsi que le soutien de l'UE dans le cadre des deux piliers de la politique agricole commune. Elle identifie deux objectifs principaux dans l'utilisation des registres : d'une part, il existe des registres axés sur la transparence, c'est-à-dire des registres dont l'objectif est de publier des données sur les subventions accordées aux bénéficiaires d'aides individuelles, principalement à des fins de contrôle (par exemple, les registres des aides d'État). D'autres registres ont pour objectif de permettre aux autorités de gérer les subventions, comme le système intégré de gestion et de contrôle (SIGC).

Dieser Beitrag befasst sich mit den auf EU-Recht basierenden Registern und ihren Zwecken im Zusammenhang mit der Gewährung staatlicher Beihilfen im Agrarsektor sowie der EU-Unterstützung im Rahmen der beiden Säulen der Gemeinsamen Agrarpolitik. Es werden zwei Hauptzwecke der Nutzung von Registern identifiziert: Einerseits gibt es transparenzorientierte Register, d.h. Register, deren Zweck darin besteht, Daten über Subventionen an einzelne Beihilfeempfänger hauptsächlich zu Kontrollzwecken zu veröffentlichen (z.B. Register für staatliche Beihilfen). Andere Register verfolgen den Zweck, den Behörden die Verwaltung von Subventionen zu ermöglichen, wie das Integrierte Verwaltungs- und Kontrollsystem (InVeKoS).

This contribution will first focus on the sources of registers and their purposes. It will then look at the implementation of transparency-driven register provisions by the Member States and will finally summarise the state of play of publication requirements in the agricultural sector.

There are two kinds of registers:

1. Transparency-driven registers

Firstly, there are “transparency-driven” registers.

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a) Transparency registers for State aid purposes

As regards the agricultural sector, such a transparency register is required under the Agricultural Block Exemption Regulation (EU) No 702/2014¹ and also under the agricultural State aid Guidelines². According to Article 108 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, Member States are under an obligation to notify any new State aid they wish to introduce. However, under certain conditions, Member States are exempt from this notification obligation³. The cases in which Member States are exempt from the notification obligation as well as the conditions under which these exemptions apply, are provided for in Regulation (EU) No 702/2014. Any aid that is not covered by that Regulation (or any other horizontal block exemption Regulation⁴) has to be notified. The State aid Guidelines provide for the conditions under which the Commission will authorise State aid notified to it. Both instruments (block exemption Regulation and Guidelines) contain a clause that any individual aid award exceeding a certain threshold⁵ has to be published on a comprehensive State aid website at national or regional level. The Commission has developed a website, the so-called “Transparency Award Module, TAM”, which Member States may use to comply with their publication obligations. All Member States with the exception of Poland, Romania and Spain make use of the TAM and publish the required data on that website, whereas the mentioned three Member States operate their publication obligation on the basis of own, national or regional registers.

¹ Commission Regulation (EU) No 702/2014 of 25 June 2014 declaring certain categories of aid in the agricultural and forestry sectors and in rural areas compatible with the internal market in application of Articles 107 and 108 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, OJ L 193, 1.7.2014, p. 1 (the so-called Agricultural Block Exemption Regulation, ABER).

² European Union Guidelines for State aid in the agricultural and forestry sectors and in rural areas 2014 to 2020, OJ C 204, 1.7.2014, p. 1.

³ See Council Regulation (EU) 2015/1588 of 13 July 2015 on the application of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union to certain categories of horizontal State aid, OJ L 248, 24.9.2015, p. 1 (the so-called “Enabling Regulation”).

⁴ In particular Commission Regulation (EU) No 651/2014 of 17 June 2014 declaring certain categories of aid compatible with the internal market in application of Articles 107 and 108 of the Treaty, OJ L 187, 26.6.2014, p. 1 (the so-called General Block Exemption Regulation, GBER).

⁵ The threshold is currently fixed at EUR 60 000 for beneficiaries active in the primary agricultural production and at EUR 500 000 for beneficiaries active in the sectors of the processing of agricultural products, the marketing of agricultural products, the forestry sector or activities falling outside the scope of Article 42 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, see Article 9(2)(c) of Regulation (EU) No 702/2014 and recital 128(c) of the Guidelines.

• b) Transparency driven registers under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)

Article 98 of Regulation (EU) 2021/2116⁶ in conjunction with Article 49(3) and (4) of the Common Provisions Regulation (EU) 2021/1060⁷ require to disclose the names of undertakings receiving aid under the two agricultural funds⁸ (EAFRD and EAGF).

Under these provisions, Member States are bound to publish aid to individual beneficiaries if the amount of aid received in one year by that beneficiary is more than EUR 1250⁹.

Transparency-driven registers therefore exist in the agricultural sector in relation to the granting of State aid (competition) and also under the CAP itself.

To identify the purpose of the registers, in the recitals of the agricultural block exemption Regulation the following motivation can be found¹⁰:

“Given that State aid within the meaning of Article 107(1) of the Treaty is, in principle, prohibited, it is important for all parties to be able to check whether an aid is granted in compliance with the applicable rules. Transparency of State aid is, therefore, essential for the correct application of Treaty rules and leads to better compliance, greater accountability, peer review and ultimately more effective public spending.”

By this recital the Commission made it clear that the purpose of the transparency register is indeed to open the possibility to peers, stakeholders, authorities etc. to ensure that aid is actually spent within the boundaries of the rules.

If one looks at the recitals of the CAP Regulation the relevant recital says¹¹:

“The publication of the name of the beneficiaries of the EAGF and EAFRD provides a means of reinforcing the public control of the use of those funds and is necessary to ensure an adequate level of protection of the Union’s financial interest. That is achieved partly by the preventive and deterrent effect of such publication, partly by discouraging individual beneficiaries from irregular behaviour and also partly by reinforcing the personal accountability of the farmers for use of public funds received.”

Therefore, the purpose of the register in this case is the reinforcement of public control and the protection of the Union’s financial interest.

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2021/2116 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 on the financing, management and monitoring of the common agricultural policy and repealing Regulation (EU) No 1306/2013, OJ L 435, 6.12.2021, p. 187.

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2021 laying down common provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund Plus, the Cohesion Fund, the Just Transition Fund and the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund and financial rules for those and for the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund, the Internal Security Fund and the Instrument for Financial Support for Border Management and Visa Policy.

⁸ The European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund, EAGF).

⁹ See Article 98(4) second subparagraph of Regulation (EU) 2021/2116.

¹⁰ Recital 32 of Regulation (EU) No 702/2014.

¹¹ Recital 78 of Regulation (EU) 2021/2116.

To summarise the purpose of transparency-driven registers, it can therefore be said that such registers intend to:

- increase market discipline on the company side because competitors of aid recipients and other interested parties will be able to see which companies have received aid, how much and for what purpose;
- promote accountability and more effective policies;
- enable market monitoring and market discipline of public spending, thus contributing to a level playing field between companies and between Member States.

2. Management driven registers

The second type of registers introduced at EU level is management-driven.

a) De minimis aid registers

This is the case with regard to the obligatory introduction of a de minimis register and has, so far, only been established in the context of the agricultural de minimis Regulation (EU) No 1408/2013¹². The background is as follows:

Under the de minimis Regulation (EU) No 1408/2013, Member States may grant aid of up to EUR 20 000 to a given beneficiary in the course of any period of three fiscal years. Moreover, the Regulation fixes in its Annex I the overall amount of de minimis aid, which a Member State is allowed to grant within any given period of three fiscal year in total, i.e. there is also a Member State cap¹³. In order to receive de minimis aid, the farmers have to declare themselves how much they have received over the last three fiscal years as de minimis aid. This system obviously has its weaknesses because the Member States' authorities have to rely on self-declarations by the farmers whose correctness they cannot verify. The risk of errors is therefore likely to be rather high. This is why the Commission has been calling upon Member States to introduce de minimis registers for reasons of more accuracy and certainty. Finally, in 2019 the Commission decided¹⁴ to render the use of a de minimis register obligatory in the following case: the Commission came to the conclusion that Member States may grant more than EUR 20 000 to a given farmer in the course of any given period of three fiscal years, namely EUR 25 000, provided the Member State concerned manages the aid grants on the basis of a de minimis register. At the same time, the Commission also increased the national cap per Member State provided it manages de minimis aid on the basis of a register¹⁵. The Commission concluded in its assessment of the risk of distortion of competition of such aid that that risk increases considerably if more than half of these caps are granted as de minimis aid to a given agricultural production sector. The production sectors are referred to in Article 2(3) of the agricultural de minimis Regulation (EU) No

¹² Commission Regulation (EU) No 1408/2013 of 18 December 2013 on the application of Articles 107 and 108 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union to de minimis aid in the agriculture sector, OJ L 352, 24.12.2013, p. 9.

¹³ This cap is fixed for all Member States in Annex I to Regulation (EU) No 1408/2013 as amended by Regulation (EU) 2019/316.

¹⁴ Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/316 ...

¹⁵ This cap is fixed for all Member States in Annex II to Regulation (EU) No 1408/2013 as amended by Regulation (EU) 2019/316.

1408/21013 as amended by Regulation (EU) 2019/316. According to that Article, these sectors are those listed in Article 1(2)(a) to (w) of the Common Market Organisation Regulation of the CAP (EU) No 1308/213¹⁶, e.g. the milk and milk products sector, the beef and veal sector, the wine sector, the rice sector, the cereals sector, etc. So Member States may grant as de minimis aid up to half of their national cap to a given agricultural sector, provided the aid is managed on the basis of a de minimis register.

In comparison to the above-mentioned transparency-driven registers, Regulation (EU) 2019/316 introducing the register into the agricultural de minimis Regulation says in its recitals¹⁷:

“Presently, it is optional for Member States to use a national central register to verify that neither the de minimis individual ceiling, nor the national cap is exceeded. However, the use of a central register would become necessary in those Member States that opt for a higher individual ceiling and national cap, given that the sector cap which is a condition for that option calls for an even closer monitoring of the aid granted.”

The purpose of de minimis registers is therefore not driven by the needs identified above in respect of transparency-driven registers, i.e. control, but by the need to manage de minimis aid, in other words to make a tool available that ensures that the maximum amount of de minimis aid is not exceeded and, in the case of the agricultural de minimis Regulation, that not more than half of the national caps are spent in favour of a given agricultural sector.

b) Registers under the CAP

When in 1992 direct payments, i.e. area-aid and animal aid premiums, were introduced in order to compensate farmers for the end of far reaching intervention buying systems, there was a need to introduce also a specific tool through which the thousands of aid applications could be managed, areas and animals be identified and be attributed to individual aid beneficiaries, the size of the areas for which aid applications are submitted, be measured and animals (bovine sheep and goats) be pursued and also be attributed to individual aid beneficiaries¹⁸. This Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) has since existed and finds its legal basis now in Chapter II or Title IV (Articles 65 et seq.) of Regulation (EU) 2021/2116.

Linked to the IACS is the system for the identification and registration of kept animals laid down by Part IV, Title I, Chapter 2, Section 1 of Regulation (EU) 2016/429¹⁹, normally referred to as the I&R system. The I&R system was introduced in order to identify and register bovine animals as a reaction

¹⁶ Regulation (EU) No 1308/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 December 2013 establishing a common organisation of the markets in agricultural products and repealing Council Regulations (EEC) No 922/72, (EEC) No 234/79, (EC) No 1037/2001 and (EC) No 1234/2007, OJ L 347, 20.12.2013, p. 671.

¹⁷ Recital 5 of Regulation (EU) 2019/316 amending Regulation (EU) No 1408/2013.

¹⁸ This system was first established by Council Regulation (EEC) No 3508/92 of 27 November 1992 establishing an integrated administration and control system for certain Community aid schemes, OJ L 355, 5.12.1992, p. 1. The legal basis has since changed several times and the IACS nowadays finds its legal basis in Regulation (EU) 2021/2116.

¹⁹ Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on transmissible animal diseases and amending and repealing certain acts in the area of animal health ('Animal Health Law'), OJ L 84, 31.3.2016, p. 1.

to the crisis triggered by the appearance of bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE). Under this system, bovine animals have to be identified in several ways (ear tags, passports) and have to be registered in a specific I&R database, which allows to track down all bovine animals and their location at any moment in time. While the I&R system has in the first place been established for health protection reasons, it is also being used to establish whether given aid beneficiaries have been the keeper of the animals for which they claim aid during the length of the minimum period required.

Both the IACS itself as well as the I&R system have been established for management purposes, i.e. to manage aid applications and the verification (control) thereof in the case of the IACS and to manage the existence and the movement of bovine animals in the case of the I&R system, notably the I&R database.

3. Conclusions

To summarise these considerations, it can be concluded that:

- there are different areas for which EU law provides for the introduction of registers, i.e. State aid, the CAP, de minimis aid;
- the purposes of the registers differ to the extent that some registers have been introduced for transparency, i.e. control purposes, whereas other registers are intended to enable the Member States to manage the procedures for the granting of aid.